

1 Tapping into skeletal muscle biomechanics for
2 design and control of lower-limb exoskeletons: a
3 narrative review

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Abstract

Lower-limb exoskeletons and exosuits (“exos”) are traditionally designed with a strong focus on mechatronics and actuation, whereas the “human-side” is often disregarded or minimally modelled. Muscle biomechanics principles and skeletal muscle response to robot-delivered loads should be incorporated in design/control of exos. In this narrative review, we summarize the advances in literature with respect to the fusion of muscle biomechanics and lower-limb exoskeletons. We reported methods to measure muscle biomechanics directly and indirectly and summarized the studies that incorporated muscle measures for improved design and control of intuitive lower-limb exos. Finally, we delved into articles that studied how the human-exo interaction influenced muscle biomechanics during locomotion. To support neurorehabilitation and facilitate everyday use of wearable assistive technologies, we believe that future studies should investigate and predict how exoskeleton assistance strategies would structurally remodel skeletal muscle over time. Real-time mapping of the neuromechanical origin and generation of muscle force resulting in joint torques should be combined with musculoskeletal models to address time varying parameters such as adaptation to exos and fatigue. Development of smarter predictive controllers that steer rather than assist biological components could result in a synchronized human-machine system that optimizes the biological and electromechanical performance of the combined system.

Keywords:

musculoskeletal modelling, human locomotion, human-machine interaction, sensor based control

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Introduction

46 Lower-limb exoskeletons and exosuits are worn in parallel with the body to assist,
47 augment, or otherwise affect mobility. Collectively referred to as “exos”, exoskeletons and
48 exosuits are often used in gait rehabilitation or as a mobility aid. ¹ Exos deliver mechanical
49 assistance to targeted biological joint(s) and thus interact directly with the wearer’s
50 musculoskeletal system. To effectively unload or augment the biological joint, knowledge of joint
51 biomechanics is typically incorporated into the design or control of the exo. Generally speaking,
52 the research field has a good comprehension of lower-limb joint-level biomechanics including:
53 dynamic (quasi-)stiffness, ²⁻⁶ distribution of work across the joints, ⁷⁻⁹ and how factors such as
54 speed, terrain, and load change the joint dynamics. ¹⁰⁻¹² However, skeletal muscles are the actual
55 actuators that generate movement. ^{13,14} Therefore, there are clear advantages to movement support
56 technology which interacts at the muscle level.

57 The quantity of published research, which combines muscle/tendon biomechanics with
58 exos is small, but exhibits a slow upwards trends in recent years. Figure 1 illustrates the long-
59 standing and increasing interest in muscle/tendon biomechanics research. The increase in exo
60 research is comparatively more recent, likely due to technological advancements improving the
61 feasibility of exo research. ¹⁵ Emerging in 2005, published research combining the fields of exos
62 and muscle/tendon biomechanics has slowly increased, although it still trails behind both of its
63 components.

64 Understanding of muscle-level biomechanics has improved with time, facilitated by
65 improvements in technology and modelling. Well established techniques, like ultrasound, were
66 able to capture muscle mechanics in intact humans *in vivo* during stationary tasks. ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
67 Improvements in technology allowed capture of muscle mechanics in dynamic situations such as

68 walking.¹⁹⁻²¹ Advances in high-density electromyography (HD-EMG) and blind source separation
69 enabled measuring the firing activity of contractile microstructures (*i.e.*, motor units) in human
70 muscles *in vivo*,^{22,23} which was critical to understanding how whole-body movement is
71 accomplished via fibre contraction at the microscale.²⁴ Computational muscle-level models
72 combined with a rise in open-source platforms and models, and an increase in computing power
73 also served to advance our understanding of muscle-level biomechanics at macro- and microscale.
74 Improvements in implementing trajectory optimization for musculoskeletal modelling facilitated
75 faster modelling and simulations, which allowed researchers to more easily simulate and
76 investigate numerous models.²⁵ In 2015, a modelling toolbox called CEINMS, integrated
77 electromyographic (EMG) driven and EMG-informed algorithms into the musculoskeletal
78 modelling environment of OpenSim.²⁶ The resulting open-source neuromusculoskeletal
79 modelling platform was able to better simulate, test, and understand how muscle activity controls
80 movement. Researchers have also developed tools to facilitate advanced optimal control (Moco in
81 OpenSim) and customizable control (SCONE) in neuromuscular simulations.^{27,28} Furthermore,
82 recent advancements have combined computationally fast musculoskeletal models with
83 reinforcement learning to explore muscle mechanics during real-life tasks. MyoSuite, an open-
84 source framework with reinforcement learning capable musculoskeletal models, enables *in silico*
85 design of robotic devices and controllers, thereby speeding up the design of personalized exos for
86 *in vivo* real-world applications.^{29,30} With a better understanding of muscle-level biomechanics we
87 gleaned insights into the mechanisms of mobility and biomechanical principles about which
88 exoskeletons can be designed and controlled.

89 Traditionally, the key players in exo design and control have been mechatronic and
90 actuation aspects, while the human aspects have often been disregarded or minimally incorporated.

91 Many exoskeletons, both old and new, exclusively use techniques other than muscle-level
92 biomechanics for their controllers and design. A number of review articles discuss the state-of-
93 the-art for non-muscle-level exoskeleton control and design,^{1,31-33} so we only briefly summarize
94 them here. Generally, exo design and control focuses on the robotic part of the human-robot
95 system, placing high importance on the output torque of the device (*Figure 2*). Oftentimes, exos
96 use position or torque tracking to enforce a pre-defined kinematic or kinetic profile, and the human
97 must yield and adapt to the robot's actuation rather than working symbiotically.³⁴⁻³⁷ Impedance
98 control considers the interaction between human and robot, resulting in a controller that is
99 responsive to the human while still enforcing predetermined dynamics.³⁷⁻⁴⁰ Volitional controllers,
100 such as proportional myoelectric controllers, further shift the controller focus from the robot to the
101 human component of the human-robot system by using human measures to inform the output.⁴¹⁻
102⁴³ However, proportional myoelectric controllers measure the emergent behaviour of the
103 underlying muscle actions and therefore do not fully capture the muscle mechanics. Human-in-
104 the-loop optimization acts to tune the exo parameters to optimize for a chosen output parameter
105 which is often human energy expenditure or muscle activity.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ Although a powerful and state-
106 of-the-art technique, human-in-the-loop optimization can be time intensive and risks falling into
107 local minima traps. Some consideration to muscle properties have also been included in design –
108 most noticeably exos which employ contractile elements mimicking musculoskeletal properties,
109 such as the McKibben pneumatic actuator (commonly referred to as an “artificial muscle”).^{41,47}
110 However, McKibben actuators require a compressed air source, thus limiting the locations the exo
111 can be used in. In addition to little incorporation of muscle-level biomechanics in exo design and
112 control, no exo has taken into consideration the short- and long-term response of skeletal muscle

113 to robot-delivered mechanical loads. Inclusion of muscle-level biomechanics may overcome some
114 shortfalls in current exo design and control.

115 The design and control of exos has been increasingly inspired by muscle-level
116 biomechanics over time. Earlier exoskeletons had heavy and bulky form factors, with a focus on
117 providing enough power to compensate for 100% of biological joint torque-generating capacity.
118 ^{48,49} Time and experience led to smaller, and less-bulky exos, with a wide variety of actuation
119 methods. The development of light-weight yet strong materials, more compact powerful batteries
120 and motors, and innovative design all contributed to reducing the bulk and weight of exos.
121 Artificial pneumatic muscles which attempted to mimic biological muscle properties and were
122 originally developed for prosthesis use, became a popular actuation method for exos.^{41,47,50,51}
123 Linear springs, acting in-line with muscle-tendon units such as the *triceps surae* complex, have
124 also been used in exo design as a form of musculotendon mimicry.^{52,53} Straps and cables, a more
125 recent form of exo actuation, are often inspired by biological tendons.^{54,55} While these techniques
126 are guided by muscle properties, none of them rely on muscle-level biomechanics, which is the
127 next logical step for exo development.

128 Inclusion of muscle-level biomechanics in exo design/control has the potential to break
129 through some of the barriers to wide-spread exo success. Despite technological advancements,
130 there is substantial room for improvement in exo design/control, particularly for real world
131 environments. In this narrative review, we will discuss how muscle-level biomechanics has been
132 and could be effectively implemented in exo control and design. We introduce the techniques and
133 hardware used to understand muscle-level biomechanics and then discuss how muscle-level
134 biomechanics can inform design and personalization. Next, we consider control choices and
135 integrating real-time muscle-level biomechanics estimators within robotic control logics. After

136 presenting how muscle-level biomechanics affects the human-machine interaction, we end the
137 review with recommendations and predictions of research within muscle-level biomechanics and
138 lower-limb exos. Throughout the manuscript, we classified techniques as “Direct” if they
139 measured a muscle property through sensors, and “Indirect” if the technique used a
140 musculoskeletal model with or without sensor input to estimate a muscle property.

141 **Measuring muscle biomechanics**

142 Incorporation of muscle biomechanics into exo design, control, or personalization requires
143 a method to measure or estimate muscle biomechanics. The measurement or estimation technique
144 usually needs to provide relevant biomechanical data *in vivo*, real-time (not for evaluation
145 purposes), and during dynamic movement. Furthermore, sensors should be compatible with the
146 physical structure of the exo. In this section, we reviewed muscle measurement methods and
147 sensors to measure or estimate muscle biomechanics that meet the requirements for use with
148 exoskeletons.

149 ***Direct measures***

150 While various sensing methods measure parameters that can provide information about muscle-
151 level kinetics and kinematics, the depth and accuracy of measurements are different. We presented
152 the methods in order from the deepest to most superficial measurements.

153 *Sarcomere Microendoscopy*

154 Sarcomere microendoscopy can directly measure the second-harmonic frequencies of light
155 generated in the muscle fibres to visualize muscle sarcomeres and their contractile dynamics.
156 Llewellyn *et al.*⁵⁶ showed that second-harmonic generation with 920 nm illumination can
157 effectively visualize sarcomeres in human extensor digitorum muscle *in vivo*. They showed that

158 visualizing sarcomere contractile dynamics in millisecond scale resolution can overcome cardiac
159 and respiratory motion artifacts which is possible through high-speed data acquisition.
160 As sarcomere length determines force production capacity in muscles, microendoscopy can reveal
161 muscle biomechanics *in vivo* while being minimally invasive. Sanchez *et al.*⁵⁷ developed a
162 wearable microendoscope to visualize sarcomere twitch dynamics in individual motor units of
163 major skeletal muscles including *soleus* and *vastus lateralis*. Although sarcomere microendoscopy
164 is still an invasive method and it has never been used in conjunction with exoskeletons, it is a
165 potential measurement method which can deepen the knowledge of muscle biomechanics to
166 inform design, control, and individualization of lower limb exoskeletons. For instance, because
167 many movement disorders exhibit or originate from disruptions in sarcomere structure and
168 performance, rehabilitative exos could be designed based on how they affect motor unit contractile
169 dynamics and the structure of sarcomeres in short- and long- term. Similarly, different types of
170 exos can take advantage of the evaluation of user adaptation and how adaptation results in desired
171 or undesired remodelling in the muscle, which is advantageous for real-world applications.

172 Sarcomere microendoscopy demonstrated how joint angle affects sarcomere length and
173 contractile dynamic. Cromie *et al.*⁵⁸ measured sarcomere length in *carpi radialis brevis* while wrist
174 was in flexion and extension. The results showed substantial sarcomere length variability in an
175 individual fibre. More studies addressed how joint angle changes sarcomere length and affects
176 muscle force generating capacity in lower limbs.^{59,60} As the changes in the sarcomere length at
177 different angles were in the range of 2 to 4 μm for the *soleus* and the measurement precision of the
178 method is ~ 30 nm, the measurement is therefore suitable for tracking the length of sarcomeres in
179 lowerlimb movement.⁶⁰ Additionally, Lichtwark *et al.*⁶¹ showed that fascicle length change can
180 represent sarcomere length change.

181 Furthermore, sarcomere microendoscopy can equip research in the field of lower limb exos
182 to investigate muscle adaptation. Pincheria *et al.*⁶² determined how three weeks of eccentric
183 exercise training changes sarcomeres in *biceps femoris long head*. They estimated sarcomere
184 length and number as well as fascicle length before and after the training. The results showed an
185 increase in the sarcomere length while the sarcomere numbers in series did not change, as well as
186 a heterogeneous change in fascicle length.

187 *Ultrasound imaging*

188 Ultrasonography enables deriving muscle architectural (*e.g.*, volume, pennation angle,
189 physiological cross-sectional area) and functional parameters (*e.g.*, fascicle kinematics), which are
190 critical to understanding muscle biomechanics. As muscles are in series with tendons, other
191 common biological measurements like joint kinematics and kinetics, or EMG cannot provide
192 enough details to measure the separate kinetics and kinematics of muscles and tendons without
193 many assumptions and models. Muscle-tendon biomechanics can provide useful information for
194 individualization, fatigue recognition, real-time and overground joint torque estimation etc., which
195 can enhance control and design in lower-limb exos.

196 Fukunaga *et al.*⁶³ used real-time ultrasonography to determine fascicle length and pennation angle
197 of human *vastus lateralis* muscle *in vivo* and non-invasively at rest and during static contraction.
198 Ultrasonography enabled *in vivo* measuring of parameters that can inform muscle level kinetics
199 and kinematics such as physiological cross-sectional area of muscles,⁶⁴ investigating differences
200 in longitudinal strain of the Achilles tendon,⁶⁵ as well as studying force-velocity behaviour of the
201 *medial gastrocnemius* muscle-tendon unit.⁶⁶ Manual tracking of muscle architectures with
202 ultrasonography is subjective and time-consuming, which led to algorithms developed for
203 automated tracking of fascicle length,⁶⁷ for which the accuracy and repeatability is assessed,⁶⁸

204 and the source code and standalone version of the semi-automated fascicle tracking algorithm was
205 made open-source.⁶⁹

206 Recently, studies used muscle ultrasonography during gait to estimate parameters like
207 volitional motion or ability and muscle power, which can be useful for exo control. For instance,
208 Nuckols *et al.*⁷⁰ used ultrasound imaging to estimate the onset of *soleus* concentric contraction just
209 before push off, when the *soleus* begins to generate positive power, in real time during various gait
210 conditions. They showed that an exo control strategy based on muscle positive power could adapt
211 to the individuality of contraction timing (e.g., healthy and post stroke patient) and how it changed
212 with changes in gait (e.g., speed and incline). Nuckols *et al.* also compared gait segmentation based
213 on automated ultrasound detection of the *soleus* contraction onset with ground reaction forces and
214 found the error was within 1% of the gait cycle. Other approaches to link human mechanics to exo
215 control strategies include optimization and grid search (i.e. parameter sweeping) which explore
216 and determine appropriate exo control parameters for a specific gait condition.⁷¹ However, both
217 techniques are time-consuming and not necessarily generalizable to differences in gaits and
218 terrains. Direct EMG or matching to kinetics and kinematics of joints are also approaches that try
219 to intuitively adapt to human gait, but their performance is not as good as optimization or grid
220 sweep. One possible reason is that joint kinetics and kinematics and EMG cannot completely
221 determine the dynamic state of muscles that are the real actuators of human gait.

222 Moreover, muscle architecture can be input into data-driven (e.g., using machine learning) or
223 mechanistic (e.g., musculoskeletal modelling) models that can estimate motion intention.
224 Jahnandish *et al.*⁷² performed image enhancement and model fitting to extract ultrasound features
225 of *rectus femoris* muscle, namely thickness, angle between aponeuroses, pennation angle, fascicle
226 length, and image echogenicity. The echogenicity, defined as the ability to send and receive an

227 ultrasound wave, was measured by averaging the intensity of all pixels in the region of interest.
228 Then, they estimated knee joint angle and angular velocity during non-weight-bearing knee
229 flexion/extension based on the trained model with an average root mean square error value of 7.45°
230 and 0.262 rad/s , which is close to a similar study which used sEMG. Muscle thickness and image
231 echogenicity showed the highest correlation with both angle and angular velocity. Also, some
232 studies showed that inputs from both s-EMG and ultrasound images (fascicle length and pennation
233 angle) can increase accuracy of ankle joint moment prediction by machine learning⁷³ models or
234 neural and musculoskeletal⁷⁴ models.

235 While studies used ultrasound B-mode probes to extract fascicle kinematics based on 2D
236 images, Yan *et al.*⁷⁵ developed a measurement system to use ultrasound wearable A-mode probes
237 (1D measurement) to estimate the acoustic nonlinearity parameter of skeletal muscles *in vivo*. The
238 acoustic non-linearity parameter changes in tissues due to diseases or residual stress, which
239 suggested that similar changes may occur with contraction in muscles. Yan *et al.* showed high
240 correlation between the acoustic nonlinearity parameter of *biceps brachii* muscle and elbow joint
241 torque, with an average coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.861. Hence, they proposed the
242 acoustic nonlinearity parameter as supplementary information for force control of exoskeletons.

243 *Shear wave tensiometry*

244 An emerging research technique to directly and non-invasively measure superficial tendon and
245 ligament kinetics is shear wave tensiometry.⁷⁶ The non-invasive device is placed on the skin,
246 directly over the target tendon or ligament. A vibrational stimulus is delivered to the tendon (via
247 the skin) which propagates through the tendon at a speed dependent on the tendon axial load due
248 to real-time characteristics of the tendon modulating the propagation of the vibration. The shear

249 wave speed can be calculated knowing the distance between two miniature accelerometers placed
250 along the tendon direction and measuring the arrival time of the propagated signal.

251 Shear wave tensiometry shows promising capabilities for applications in lower limb exos.
252 First, it is applicable to lower limb exos, as the impulses are detectable throughout the gait cycle
253 and can track dynamically varying wave speed.⁷⁷ Several studies used shear wave tensiometry to
254 track the dynamics of standing balance and measure gait kinetics in clinical and able-bodied
255 populations, including children, adults, and older adults^{78–82}. Second, in more dynamic tasks like
256 running and jumping, Schmitz *et al.*⁸³ proposed adding redundant accelerometers and using a
257 Kalman filter to mitigate random sensor noise due to the high rate of loading and impact events.
258 Harper *et al.*⁸⁴ developed a wearable shear wave tensiometer with dynamic range to track
259 unconstrained locomotion. A later work combined this with inertial measurement units⁸⁵ to
260 measure the work and power output of *Triceps Surae* outdoors. Schneebeli *et al.*⁸⁶ used intraclass
261 correlation coefficient (ICC3.1) to test the test-retest (ICC3.1 0.87–0.99), inter-session (ICC3.1
262 0.75–0.93) and intra-session (ICC3.1 0.85–0.96) reliability of shear wave tensiometry, which
263 shows promising use in clinical and research settings.

264 *High Density Electromyography (HD-EMG)*

265 Non-invasive and flexible or woven textile bi-dimensional grids of electrodes can measure
266 muscle high density electromyograms (HD-EMGs).⁸⁷ HD-EMG is an interferent electrical signal
267 generated by the superposition of action potentials generated by hundreds of skeletal muscle fibres
268 during contraction. Because skeletal muscle fibres are directly innervated by alpha motor neurons
269 (neural cells residing in the spinal cord), the HD-EMGs carry information about alpha motor
270 neuron activity, which is directly associated to the control of movements.⁸⁸ Blind source
271 separation can be used to disentangle the interferent HD-EMG and decode both discharge timings

272 of motor neurons as well as the resulting action potentials travelling along innervated skeletal
273 fibres. HD-EMG holds great potential to explore the neuro-mechanics of movement in individuals
274 wearing exoskeletons. Many studies have addressed HD-EMG in upper limb gesture recognition
275 and exoskeleton controllers, but the literature in lower limb exoskeletons is scarce.

276 Some studies investigated HD-EMG during locomotion and demonstrated that spatial
277 patterns of electromyograms can reveal how muscles adapt to different locomotion modes. Schlink
278 *et al.*²³ compared different signal processing methods to reduce motion artifacts in HD-EMG
279 during human locomotion and proposed canonical correlation analysis filtering during fast walking
280 and running. Schlink *et al.*⁸⁹ also showed that spatial patterns of electromyograms are
281 heterogeneous and differ among lower limb muscles and locomotion speeds, which could be due
282 to preferential recruitment of faster motor units under greater loads. Moreover, they showed that
283 fatigue alters spatial myoelectric patterns in the *medial gastrocnemius* during locomotion, while
284 lower limb biomechanics remains similar, a potential strategy to avoid overuse injuries.⁹⁰ Exos
285 can use HD-EMG to recognize fatigue or locomotion mode to tune assistance (e.g., timing and
286 magnitude of torque). Also, HD-EMG can reveal muscle recruitment strategies, impairments, and
287 adaptations of users as valuable information for exoskeleton design.

288 *Force myography (FMG)*

289 FMG refers to a broad category of methods that non-invasively measure muscle
290 biomechanics by quantifying how muscle external geometry changes. FMG usually includes an
291 array of sensors to detect muscle deformation or stiffness due to contraction, and methods that
292 process the collected data to extract the desired parameters. FMG can vary in type of sensors (e.g.,
293 force or pressure sensors, strain sensors, bending sensors), sensor arrangement, and data
294 processing method (e.g. signal processing and feature extraction, machine learning techniques),

295 with specific limitations associated with each technique.³⁷ However, sensor characteristics and
296 device configuration can adversely affect the reliability of FMG signals. For instance, many
297 researchers calibrated the pre-load forces when the device is donned based on the user's oral
298 feedback.⁹¹ Moreover, some methods are based on cross-sectional area increase of the muscles.⁹²
299 These methods can be used in some applications like gesture recognition but cannot estimate
300 individual muscle force without making assumptions on the contribution of the individual muscles
301 to the cross-sectional area increase. Also, some techniques are only applicable to static situations
302 as they cannot handle motion artifacts.⁹³

303 Some recent studies developed and used soft and wearable strain sensors to monitor muscle
304 contractions.^{92,94} Alvares *et al.*⁹⁴ used sensors based on strain-mediated contact in anisotropically
305 resistive structures (SCARS) to measure changes in muscle deformation which correlate with
306 muscle input and knee torque.

307 Many studies include FMG in hand rehabilitative and assistive exoskeletons to enhance
308 user intention in upper body,⁹⁵⁻⁹⁹ but FMG in lower limb applications is limited. Jiang *et al.*¹⁰⁰
309 proposed a wearable gait phase determination system based on FMG. The proposed force
310 myography band could correctly detect more than 99.9% of gait phases over 12965 gait phase
311 segments with an average temporal error of 55.2 ms. With upper limb applications motivating
312 hardware and processing improvements in FMG, there is an increased likelihood of interesting
313 applications for lower limb exos in the future.

314 ***Indirect measures***

315 Aside from the direct measurements mentioned above, real-time musculoskeletal models
316 have been used to estimate biomechanical parameters *in vivo*, such as muscle-tendon forces,¹⁰¹

317 kinematics, joint torques, ^{102,103} joint stiffness, ^{5,6} and compressive loads, ¹⁰⁴ which can be used in
318 exoskeleton controls, ¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁸ without using invasive measurement sensors.

319 One research direction is to use optimization to estimate individual muscle forces from the
320 net joint torques (often got from inverse dynamics^{109,110}), named static optimization. ¹¹¹⁻¹¹⁴
321 Specifically, researchers developed real-time computing platforms that utilize the static
322 optimization method in estimating muscle forces. ^{115,116} However, optimization-based muscle
323 force estimation for lower limbs often requires force plates to measure ground reaction forces,
324 which limits this potential in out-of-lab applications. Trajectory optimization can avoid this issue
325 by modelling the ground contacts, however, the objective function is normally movement-type
326 specific and may not reflect an individual person or patient. ^{25,117} Furthermore, the computation
327 time is long and prevented it from being used in the real-time control of wearable robotic devices.

328 To solve this problem, muscle force estimation using sEMG driven musculoskeletal (MSK)
329 models have been developed, which requires joint angles and sEMG signals as input. At first, due
330 to computational complexity, studies were focused on only one joint and its corresponding
331 muscles^{118,119} and an infinitely stiff tendon model was also used in the muscle models to save in
332 computational time; ¹²⁰ Later, these types of studies were expanded to multiple joints and muscles
333 as well as incorporating an elastic tendon to cover more complex movements; ^{102,121} Recently, the
334 open source Calibrated EMG-Informed NeuroMusculoSkeletal Modelling Toolbox (CEINMS)
335 was developed to lower the entry to this field. ^{26,103} Furthermore, experimental EMG paired with
336 inverse dynamics allowed for the personalization of muscle-tendon models to the user as they
337 represent the inputs/outputs pair. ²⁶ Not only can this method estimate muscle forces, but studies
338 also demonstrated that it could accurately estimate joint torque and extrapolate results for unknown
339 tasks (not used for the muscle-tendon model parameters personalisation), and even other degrees

340 of freedom.¹²² Since musculoskeletal models were directly driven by the sEMG signals, calculated
341 muscle forces and joint torques can be prior to the electromechanical delay of actual
342 musculoskeletal systems, which provides a big advantage in exoskeleton control as it gives a
343 windows of opportunity where optimal assistance can be provided to the user.^{106,107} By knowing
344 the force of each muscle that wraps over a joint, joint stiffness^{5,6,123,124} and compressive loads can
345 be estimated.^{104,125-129} As these parameters are more closely relevant to either human-robot
346 interactions or injury risks, they are more suitable to be directly used as control parameters in
347 exoskeletons. Even though the above-mentioned studies have shown very promising results on
348 reproducing joint torques, validating the actual muscle forces in vivo on human subjects poses
349 ethical challenges, making it difficult to directly measure and validate these forces. However,
350 experimental studies conducted on cats have provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of
351 various approaches, such as static optimization, trajectory optimization, and surface
352 electromyography (sEMG).¹³⁰⁻¹³³ The similarities in muscle structures and types between humans
353 and cats support the belief that these methods can be reliable in interpreting human movements as
354 well. While there may be some species-specific differences, the fundamental principles underlying
355 muscle mechanics and control are expected to be comparable. In general, indirect measurement
356 methods provide very useful muscle biometric information using very simple sensor setups,
357 compared to direct methods, which has advantages in real-life applications.

358 **Muscle and tendon biomechanics for exoskeleton design or personalization**

359 A main objective of exos is to interact with the human wearing them. Thus, this interaction
360 will influence the design and control of the exo. For a long time, the human neuromusculoskeletal
361 system was ignored in the conception of exoskeletons resulting in devices that were powerful but
362 bulky and with little to no benefit for the user.⁴⁹ To overcome this challenge, exoskeleton

363 emulators for iterative design were established; the most established of which is the human-in-the-
364 loop technique.⁴⁶ Although emulators can result in the creation of optimal design and control,⁵²
365 they require a large amount of human data (3600 recorded conditions in the cited study).

366 ***Direct measurements***

367 Direct measurements of muscle biomechanics can provide useful information to inspire
368 novel designs or to help tune exoskeletons. Ultrasound imaging can reveal the effects of exo
369 stiffness on force production in muscles and tendons. Farris *et al.*¹³⁴ evaluated the effect of parallel
370 elastic assistance of ankle exoskeleton in hopping on *soleus* muscle-tendon-unit mechanics using
371 *in vivo* ultrasound imaging. They showed that parallel assistance to *soleus* muscle reduces muscle
372 force, but average positive fascicle power does not significantly change. This can help with tuning
373 the stiffness of lower limb exos to optimize metabolic cost. Takahashi *et al.*¹³⁵ investigated foot-
374 ankle interplay during walking by adding stiffness to the foot through shoes and insoles. They used
375 ultrasound imaging to show that a stiffer foot results in decreased shortening velocity and increased
376 force output in *soleus* muscle. The results suggested added foot/shoe stiffness as a potential design
377 parameter to improve locomotion economy in tasks where muscles should generate more muscle
378 force (e.g., walking with load carriage) or operate with less economy (e.g., fast walking speeds
379 close to the walk-to-run transition). Also, Nuckols *et al.*¹³⁶ showed how exoskeleton stiffness alters
380 *soleus* muscle contractile dynamics and affects metabolic rate during walking. They used
381 ultrasound imaging to show that exoskeletons with higher rotational stiffness increase fascicle
382 length and velocity and decrease fascicle force. However, the change in contractile dynamics
383 results in a bowl-shape metabolic cost. Hence, measuring contractile behaviour can help to design
384 or tune exos to steer more economical force production in the muscles. Moreover, Beck *et al.*¹³⁷

385 showed how artificially fast balance-correcting exoskeleton torque can improve balance by 9%
386 and how it affects fascicle mechanics.

387 Moreover, direct measurements can help exo personalisation through design and evaluation
388 of assistance profile. Nuckols *et al.*¹³⁸ demonstrated that ultrasound imaging can measure muscle
389 dynamics to develop exosuit assistance profiles that are tailored to the individual and adaptive to
390 dynamic walking tasks. Also, Schmitz *et al.*¹³⁹ used shear wave tensiometer to directly measure
391 force in the Achilles tendon during walking assisted with ankle exosuit while carrying load. They
392 performed a pilot experiment in an unconstrained outdoor environment to evaluate nine different
393 exosuit assistance profiles based on reduction in the peak force in Achilles tendon. The most
394 efficient exosuit assistance profile could reduce metabolic cost by 9.6%.

395 ***Indirect measurements***

396 Human-exoskeleton simulation can acquire the same benefits of emulators without requiring
397 a high volume of human data. As previously presented, there is a wealth of literature on
398 neuromusculoskeletal modelling based on cadaveric studies or human experiments. Nevertheless,
399 one of the main and active challenges is the simulation of how human and mechanical devices
400 interact. One of the main axes of simulation-research is based on predictive simulation using
401 optimal control, which can reproduce the interaction between the human-exoskeleton system and
402 the environment. Optimal control can also predict the effect of exos on humans or human
403 biomechanical variables in unknown conditions. Fournier *et al.* began with a biomechanical
404 simulation of healthy and spinal cord injury kinematics at varied walking speeds,¹⁴⁰ then added a
405 simulated exoskeleton to the human neuromusculoskeletal system, which allowed them to predict
406 ground reaction forces. Predictive simulation and optimal control can also be used to predict the
407 effect of exos with different mechanical properties, for example Sreenivasa *et al.*¹⁴¹ looked into

408 the optimal stiffness of an ankle-foot orthosis for reducing muscle effort in children with gait
409 abnormality and Febrer-Nafría *et al.*¹⁴² optimized parameters such as angle shape for the kinematic
410 assistance delivered through an active knee exoskeleton to a spinal cord injury (SCI) patient. In
411 both cases, after testing their simulation with pre-recorded human data, they created an
412 optimization routine that tracked real kinematics or torque parameters and/or tried to minimize
413 power, muscle activation or jerk.

414 Simulation can also be used to create a set of requirements for exos. Afschrift *et al.*
415 investigated a capability gap (torque that a weakened muscle can produce against the torque task
416 requirement computed using inverse dynamics), which allowed identification of the minimum
417 level of assistance required for people with muscle weakness (reduction of maximal force
418 capability in the muscle) to realise certain tasks.¹⁴³ This is an effective technique to determine the
419 minimum power of the actuator in the exo for people with muscle weakness. Following the same
420 philosophy, a study simulated ideal actuators to find the best single degree of freedom (DOF) or
421 multi-DOF joint to actuate to minimize metabolic cost during running.¹⁴⁴ Results showed that at
422 low running speeds (2 m/s) all joints provided the same metabolic reduction but at higher speeds,
423 the hip could create better metabolic savings. For multi-DOF, a combination of hip, knee and ankle
424 offered the highest metabolic reduction. Another interesting simulation study¹⁴⁵ showed how
425 coupled joint assistance (using the same actuator/assistance on multiple DOF) had the same or
426 similar effect on metabolic savings as multi-actuator assistance and provide better metabolic
427 reduction than assisting only one DOF. This provided important guidelines in exoskeleton design
428 to save on hardware components i.e., going from one actuator per DOF to one actuator crossing
429 multiple joints thus providing cheaper devices.

453 generation of joint torques is a useful for exoskeleton control. Direct or indirect measurement of
454 joint torque can allow creation of a symbiotic system between the human and exo by providing
455 assistance proportional to the force produced by the user (Figure 3). Although joint torque can be
456 estimated through inverse dynamics, estimation through muscle biomechanics may be more
457 suitable for exoskeletons applications, particularly applications in uncontrolled (non-laboratory)
458 environments.

459 ***Direct measurements***

460 Despite attempts and innovations to directly measure muscle biomechanics during gait or
461 other lower-limb movements to estimate useful control signals for muscle in the loop controllers
462 (e.g., estimating joint torque or fatigue), we could find only one study that actually used a direct
463 measurement of muscle biomechanics to estimate a parameter for the control parameter. Sheng *et*
464 *al.*¹⁵⁰ used real-time ultrasound-based muscle fatigue assessment to robustly control their hybrid
465 (functional electrical stimulation and electrical motor) knee exoskeleton to switch between its
466 modes and avoid extensive stimulation of the fatigued muscle.

467 ***Neuromusculoskeletal modelling***

468 One indirect way of accessing joint torque is by using a neuromusculoskeletal model fed by
469 EMG. Using neuromusculoskeletal modelling in combination with an exoskeleton is a recent
470 technique, which was primarily delayed by the limitation of achieving real-time computation of
471 the complex model (multi-DOF and multi-musculotendon unit).^{109,122} Fleischer and Hommel¹⁵¹
472 were the first to present the possibility of using a real-time neuromusculoskeletal model for the
473 control of an unilateral knee exoskeleton. Durandau *et al.*¹⁰⁵ further developed the methods to
474 apply it to a lower-limb exoskeleton for the knee and ankle and tested it on patients (SCI and
475 stroke). The results showed the possibility of using this kind of system for rehabilitation purposes,

476 where muscle effort is reduced while also reducing neural control variability. Furthermore, the
477 same system is used for a bilateral ankle exoskeleton during diverse walking conditions¹⁰⁶ showing
478 the possibility to reduce the muscular effort in variable walking speed and showing better
479 adaptability than the current state-of-the-art speed adaptive controller^{52,152} although the
480 metabolic reduction is less. Finally, neuromusculoskeletal models offer the possibility to compute
481 biomechanical variables other than joint torque, such as stiffness, which can also benefit robotic
482 control. Yao *et al.*¹⁵³ combined real-time muscle stiffness computation (*tibialis anterior*) and joint
483 torque to control a non-ambulatory ankle exoskeleton. The joint torque estimation is used as an
484 input command to the torque controller and the muscle stiffness is used to modulate the stiffness
485 coefficient of the admittance controller used for the torque controller. Nevertheless, this method
486 relies on EMG sensors which are subject to noise and muscle crosstalk as well as interference from
487 electromechanical devices (i.e. an exoskeleton).

488 Neural control models can be used to drive musculoskeletal models for exoskeletons, which
489 reduces reliance on EMG sensors. Ruiz *et al.*¹⁵⁴⁻¹⁵⁶ explored the possibility of using a motor
490 primitive-based neural control model for controlling leg exoskeletons together with
491 musculoskeletal models. They conducted experiments to evaluate the performance of the
492 neuromusculoskeletal model-based controller. A full-leg exoskeleton that had motors at the ankle,
493 knee and hip was used as the hardware platform. Participants were asked to perform a locomotion
494 track involving ground-level walking, ascending stairs, and descending stairs and several
495 transitions between these tasks. They showed that the assistance significantly decrease time to
496 perform tasks. Dzeladini *et al.*¹⁵⁷ showed that a reflex-based neuromuscular controller (NMC) for
497 an ankle orthosis can reduce the net metabolic cost compared to the transparent mode without
498 disturbing the walking dynamics at slow and normal speeds. Later, they extended the

499 neuromuscular control framework into a hip and knee robotic exoskeleton and tested it on SCI
500 patients.^{158,159} Their results showed that NMC enabled SCI subjects to walk at several speeds,
501 including near healthy speeds, in a healthy-like manner. Shafer *et al.*¹⁶⁰ implemented a simple
502 reflex-based neuromuscular controller for an ankle exoskeleton to study the effects of the reflex
503 control parameters, such as the reflex gains and reflex time delay on users. They found that the
504 reflex-based assistance could systematically reduce users' biological ankle moment, however, it
505 didn't reduce their overall metabolic cost. Until now, most studies have looked at the immediate
506 effect on the neuromusculoskeletal system, but long-term effects have not yet been investigated.
507 The direct effect of assistance on the neural system has also been overlooked.

508

509 **Changes to Muscle Biomechanics when using Lower-Limb Exoskeletons**

510 In this section, we summarized the changes to muscle biomechanics as a result of using
511 exoskeleton assisted movement. Studies investigated these changes during actuation of lower-limb
512 joints during either walking, seated knee flexion/extension, hopping, squatting, or sit-to-stand
513 tasks. The influence on plantar flexion and dorsiflexion is commonly studied when using ankle
514 exoskeletons, and are summarized in Table 1, whereas the following sections address actuation of
515 either the knee or hip joints. We also briefly discuss the studies that used commercial lower limb
516 exoskeletons or robotic gait trainers such as Lokomat and Lopes.

517 ***Active actuation of knee or hip joint***

518 Many studies showed that knee exoskeletons can reduce activity of associated muscles.
519 Some studies that actuated the knee joint provided additional passive supports at either ankle or
520 hip.¹⁶¹⁻¹⁶⁸ The results showed reductions in *soleus*,¹⁶³ *rectus femoris*, *tibialis anterior*,
521 *gastrocnemius lateralis*, and *semitendinosus*¹⁶² during gait, and during swing phase, the *biceps*

522 *femoris*,¹⁶¹ *tibialis anterior*, and *semitendinosus*¹⁶² when walking with powered as compared to
523 minimal impedance mode. In minimal impedance mode, also called “free” or “transparent” mode,
524 the exo attempts to be transparent to the user and minimally impact walking biomechanics either
525 by providing no torque or actively controlling for minimal interaction torque. Active knee
526 assistance with passive hip support reduced muscle activity of hip and knee extensors.¹⁶⁶ This
527 general decrease in EMG activity was further associated with a decreasing trend over the time with
528 assisted walking due to adaptation.¹⁶⁶

529 Studies also evaluated knee exoskeletons in other tasks such as squatting¹⁶⁷ or knee flexion-
530 extension.^{165,168} A knee exoskeleton also reduced knee extensor muscle activity when using a
531 controller that is capable of injecting the minimal amount of energy needed to support oscillations
532 of the knee.¹⁶⁵

533 Passive springs placed anteriorly on the hip stored and released energy thereby reducing plantar
534 flexor activity during walking.¹⁶⁹ Actuated hip exoskeletons increased muscle activity of *tibialis*
535 *anterior*, *rectus femoris*, and *gastrocnemius medialis* in the minimal impedance mode, whereas
536 that of the *semitendinosus* reduced.¹⁶⁴ However, providing assistance reduced the muscle activity
537 of the *tibialis anterior*, *rectus femoris*, and *gastrocnemius medialis* but increased activity of the
538 *semitendinosus*.¹⁶⁴

539 *Actuation across multiple joints, and use of Robotic Gait Trainers, and commercial* 540 *exoskeletons*

541 An exoskeleton with active knee and ankle actuation reduced muscle activity for both healthy
542 and participants with stroke in the knee flexors and extensors, and ankle plantar and dorsiflexors.
543 ¹⁰⁵ Increased assistance reduced the variability of muscle activity in this study. Lower limb
544 exoskeletons with hip and knee actuation and passive ankle support reduced muscle activity of the

545 *vastus medialis, gastrocnemius medialis,*^{170,171} *tibialis anterior, rectus femoris, soleus*¹⁷⁰ when
546 compared to walking with a minimal impedance mode. Activity of *semitendinosus* and *biceps*
547 *femoris* increased when walking slowly with the exoskeleton.¹⁷⁰ Furthermore, muscle synergy
548 patterns were shown to be altered when wearing such exoskeletons¹⁷². Otálora and colleagues¹⁷³
549 showed that actuation of the hip, knee, and ankle joints reduced activity in the knee flexors and
550 extensors, and *tibialis anterior*.

551 Gait training devices such as the LOPES and Lokomat provide different degrees of actuation
552 of the lower limb and, unlike exoskeletons, can also provide body weight support. Walking in the
553 LOPES in zero-impedance mode showed a decrease in muscle activity of the muscles involved in
554 push off whereas an increase in activity of muscles that contribute to acceleration and deceleration
555 of the swing leg.^{174,175} The activation timing was rather unchanged.¹⁷⁴ The virtual pivot point
556 model implemented in LOPES II through admittance control also showed decreased muscle
557 activity in *rectus femoris, hamstring, medial gastrocnemius, and gluteus maximus* muscles.¹⁷⁵
558 Literature about how the Lokomat impacted post training muscle activity has been inconclusive.
559 The Lokomat imposes able-bodied joint trajectories through impedance control, with varying
560 levels of exo guidance force. At higher levels of guidance force the joint trajectories are more rigid
561 and it is increasingly difficult for the muscles of the user to influence or affect the trajectory of the
562 Lokomat. The results depended on guidance level,^{176,177} speed,^{176,178} or body weight support.
563^{177,179} Walking on the Lokomat increased the activity of *biceps femoris* in healthy participants,
564^{176,177,179} *vastus lateralis*^{176,179} *erector spinae, tibialis anterior,*¹⁷⁹ *tibialis anterior* and *rectus*
565 *femoris*.¹⁷⁷ However, another study identified a general lowering of muscle activity compared to
566 treadmill walking in participants with stroke as well as healthy walkers.¹⁸⁰ For participants with
567 SCI, Lokomat training reduced *vastus lateralis* and *rectus femoris* activity during stance phase,

568 and increased *gastrocnemius medialis* during swing phase.¹⁸¹ The Lokomat was also used to
569 differentially assist either side during gait, and showed an inverse relation to muscle activity on
570 the other side.¹⁷⁸ The activity in the trunk muscles during training with the Lokomat was similar
571 to quiescent supine lying.¹⁸² Using a robotic trainer that only assisted the hip increased activity of
572 knee flexors.¹⁸³

573 Commercially available exoskeletons have been rigorously studied in literature.^{182,184–194} For
574 instance, studies reported reduction in *rectus femoris*,^{186,187} *gluteus medius*, *medial hamstring*,
575 *tibialis anterior*, *soleus*,¹⁸⁷ *gluteus maximus*, *rectus femoris*, *vastus lateralis*, and *gastrocnemius*
576 and an increase in *biceps femoris*¹⁸⁶ when walking with the Ekso GT, which assists the user in a
577 predefined trajectory. However, the change in muscle activity depended on gait phase, whether the
578 user had voluntary control in the exoskeleton, and the speed of reference walking without
579 exoskeleton.¹⁸⁶ Voluntary control increased burst duration compared to fast walking.¹⁸⁶

580 The Ekso has often used to train participants with neurological impairments.^{182,184–186,188–193}
581 Participants with multiple sclerosis showed a new muscle synergy when walking with the
582 exoskeleton.¹⁹³ Incomplete SCI participants showed non-reciprocal firing patterns and reduced
583 muscle activations especially that of the *rectus femoris*¹⁹⁰ and *tibialis anterior*.¹⁸⁶ A reduced
584 variability in muscle activity was seen when walking with the exoskeleton.¹⁹⁰ Alamro¹⁸² observed
585 an increase in trunk EMG when walking with Ekso-assisted compared to the Lokomat for SCI
586 participants. Trunk EMG activation remained similar between Ekso overground and treadmill
587 walking.

588 Stroke participants were studied at all three phases; acute, sub-acute, and chronic with the
589 Ekso.^{184,185,188,189,191,192} Participants with acute stroke showed reduction in *soleus* and *rectus*
590 *femoris* activity on affected side during stance phase with the exoskeleton.¹⁸⁴ *Vastus Lateralis* and

591 *rectus femoris* showed the largest dissimilarity in activation with the exoskeleton on the affected
592 side.¹⁸⁴ Using the Ekso for training in sub-acute stroke improved bilateral symmetry of *tibialis*
593 *anterior* and decreased co-contractions of the proximal muscles, suggesting improvement in
594 proximal muscle activity.¹⁸⁹ Activation timing for the *semitendinosus* was improved in the paretic
595 leg after training.¹⁹¹ The Ekso trained group also showed more physiological motor control in the
596 *semitendinosus* and *rectus femoris*.¹⁹¹ Chronic stroke participants who trained with the Ekso
597 showed reduced affected side *rectus femoris* activity during swing phase,¹⁸⁸ increase in *rectus*
598 *femoris*, reduction in affected *biceps femoris*, increase in unaffected *biceps femoris*, reduced *soleus*
599 and *tibialis anterior* activity was seen.¹⁸⁵ The synergy modules necessary to reconstruct lower
600 limb muscle activities were more similar to healthy walking post Ekso training.¹⁹²

601 This section overviewed the impact on muscles as a result of assistance provided by exos. In
602 sum, we see a reduction in muscle activity across joints, and tasks, as well as changes to muscle
603 synergies. This understanding must be accounted for when designing novel controllers that interact
604 with the muscle directly.

605 Discussion and future predictions

606 Exos have been designed with the goal of enhancing human movement. However, current
607 technologies have shown only modest results in healthy individuals and limited clinical impact. A
608 central element hampering progress is that exos do not interact directly with underlying skeletal
609 muscles, but instead deliver external mechanical loads that directly influence the biological
610 skeletal system. As such, current systems do not consider how biological muscles, tendons, joints,
611 react to mechanically delivered torques. In this context, research in exos has overlooked the effect
612 of robotic assistance, especially at extreme ends of the spatiotemporal scale (e.g., cell growth over
613 months or years).^{88,195} This is a critical aspect of human-exo physical interaction as skeletal

614 muscles will remodel new structural properties if exposed long enough to exo-delivered torques.
615 The current inability to predict how exo assistance strategies would remodel skeletal muscle
616 structurally hampers progress in longitudinal neurorehabilitation and in day-to-day adoption of
617 wearable assistive technologies.

618 In the future we envision research advances aimed at ‘closing-the-loop’ between exos and
619 human skeletal muscle biology.⁸⁸ In this context, we envision that future exos should be capable
620 of delivering coordinated mechanical torques to alter, in a controlled way, skeletal muscle form
621 and function over time scales ranging from seconds (e.g., a movement cycle) to months (e.g., the
622 recovery stage following a neuromuscular injury) and beyond (e.g., across ageing stages).

623 We envision this will require developments in three key directions: (1) recording both
624 neural and mechanical function underlying muscle contraction (e.g., motor neuron discharges and
625 innervated skeletal fibre force) in the intact moving human *in vivo*, (2) fusing recorded neuro-
626 mechanical data with numerical models to predict skeletal muscle adaptation in response to exos-
627 delivered torques over time and (3) developing predictive controllers to steer skeletal muscle form
628 and function with enough certainty to induce a targeted, positive change in the future. This will
629 open to a new class of muscle-centred exos that directly respond to biological cues to maintain
630 integrity of skeletal muscles over the lifespan.

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637

638 Figure 1. The number of studies published over time on exos, muscle/tendon biomechanics, and
 639 both exos & muscle-tendon biomechanics from 1965 to 2022. The data were found through the
 640 PubMed database (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). All data searches were in English and for
 641 lower limb extremities (KEYWORD: gait OR walking OR (lower AND (limb OR extremities)))
 642 in human (KEYWORD: human OR participant OR patient). Specific data searches were: A) exos
 643 (KEYWORD: (exoskelet* OR exosuit)), B) Muscle/tendon biomechanics (KEYWORD: (muscle
 644 mechanics) OR ((muscle OR tendon) AND (biomechanics))), and C) muscle/tendon biomechanics
 645 and exos (KEYWORD: (muscle mechanics) OR ((muscle OR tendon) AND (biomechanics)) AND
 646 (exoskelet* OR exosuit)).

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650 Figure 2. Visual representation of the “focus” of high level exo controllers in terms of the robot-
 651 human system. Controllers on the left of the scale prioritize the robot part of the system, while the
 652 controllers to the right of the scale focus on the human part.

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654

655 Figure 3. A general exoskeleton controller using a biomechanical model.

656

657

Tables

658 Table 1: Summary of changes to muscle-tendon biomechanics when participants wore an ankle

659 exoskeleton.

Actuation Type	Task	Muscle/Tendon(s)	Condition varied	Changes to muscle biomechanics
Passive	Hopping	Plantar flexors	Ankle joint stiffness	Decreased activity, force, and force rate ^{134,196,197} Operating at less optimal fibre length and increased fibre velocity ^{134,198} Increased fascicle excursion, and overall no change in averaged positive fascicle power ¹³⁴
Active	Walking	<i>soleus</i>	Ankle joint Stiffness	Reduced muscle force, increased fascicle length and velocity ¹³⁶
		Plantar flexors	Inclination of walking surface	Increase in inclination results in lower reductions in muscle activity ¹⁹⁹
		Plantar flexors	Exoskeleton work	Increasing work reduced activity, and increased muscle synergy weights ²⁰⁰
		<i>soleus</i>	Exoskeleton torque	Increasing torque reduced activity, and increased muscle synergy activations ²⁰⁰
		Plantar flexors	Adaptation to walking with exoskeleton	Decreased activity ²⁰¹
		<i>soleus</i>	Controller type	Gait timing controllers are better than myoelectric controller proportional to <i>soleus</i> activity ²⁰² myoelectric controller proportional to <i>gastrocnemius medialis</i> reduces <i>soleus</i> activity ²⁰³
		-	Speed, step length, and walking incline	Increased apparent efficacy with increasing speed or step length ²⁰⁴ and drops when the surface incline increases ¹⁹⁹
	Walking with load	<i>Achilles</i> tendon	With and without exo, carrying additional load	Increase in tendon force with increase in load carried, but reduced with exo assistance ¹³⁹
Walking in participants with chronic stroke	Bilateral <i>latissimus dorsi</i> , <i>erector spinae</i> , <i>external oblique</i> , hip flexors and extensors, knee flexors and extensors, plantar flexors and dorsiflexors.	With and without exo	Improved similarity of synergies in either side ²⁰⁵	

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